

Dura Europos Mithraeum

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The site of Dura Europos was built along the banks of the Euphrates river in present-day Syria. Founded as a fortified settlement in 300 BCE by the Hellenistic king, Seleukos Nikator, at a strategic location in a frontier region. It grew to develop a Hippodameian town plan (orthogonal city blocks) and strong fortification walls and gates. It was conquered by the Parthians in 113 BCE, the Romans in the 2nd c. CE, and destroyed by the Sasanids in 256 CE. Whether the city was completely abandoned after this siege is debated. Dura was a very multicultural city from its foundation as its various rulers tolerated a vast multiplicity of cultures, ethnicities, languages, and religious traditions. There were many cults from different cultures present in the city co-existing throughout its existence: Parthian, Semitic, Greek, Roman, Jewish, Christian--and hybrid manifestations of these various religious traditions. The second Roman conquest of Dura under Lucius Verus coincided with the introduction of the cult of Mithras to the city. A mithraeum (temple to Mithras) was built by Imperial troops in 168 CE in a room at a private house along the NW fortifications of the city. It was renovated and enlarged around 209 and ultimately destroyed in 256 when the space was filled in to strengthen the fortification walls for the impending Sasanid siege. The mithraeum was excavated from 1934-1935 by the joint Yale-French team excavating the city. The mithraeum was afterwards dismantled and transported to the Yale University Art Gallery.

Date Range: 168 CE - 256 CE

Region: Dura Europos Mithraeum

Region tags: Asia, Western Asia, Syrian Arab Republic, Middle East, Syria, Syria, West Asia

The site of the mithraeum at Dura Europos in present-day Syria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Vermaseren, M.J. 1956. *Corpus Inscriptionum et Monumentorum Religionis Mithriacae* (CIMRM) Vol. 1: nos.34-69.

– Source 2: Rostovtzeff, M. 1934. Das Mithraeum von Dura. MDAI 49: 180-207

– Source 3: Rostovtzeff, M., Brown, F.E., Welles, C.B. 1939. The excavations at Dura-Europos. Report of the seventh and eight seasons of work, 1933-1934 and 1934-1935. New Haven.

Notes: Beck, R. 2006. The Religion of the Mithras Cult in the Roman Empire: Mysteries of the Unconquered Sun. Oxford. Clauss, M. 1990. The Roman Cult of Mithras. New York. Cunningham, C. 1984. "The Conservation of the Mithraeum in the Yale University Art Gallery," Yale University Art Gallery Bulletin 39.2: 12-15. Dirven, L. and McCarty, M.M. "Rethinking the Dura-Europos Mithraeum: Diversification and Stabilization in a Mithraic Community." In Egri and McCarty (eds.) The Archaeology of Mithraism : New Finds and Approaches to Mithras-Worship. Peeters. pp. 165-181. Gnoli, T. 2016. "The Mithraeum of Dura-Europos: New Perspectives". In Kaizer (ed.), Religion, Society and Culture at Dura-Europos. Cambridge, pp. 126-143. Hopkins, C. 1979. The Discovery of Dura-Europos. New Haven. Kiefer, K.M. and Matheson, S.B. 1982. Life in an Eastern Province: The Roman Fortress at Dura-Europos, exh. cat. New Haven. Matheson, S.B. 1982. Dura-Europos: The Ancient City and the Yale Collection, New Haven. Walsh, D. 2018. The Cult of Mithras in Late Antiquity: Development, Decline and Demise ca. A.D. 270-430. Leiden.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://artgallery.yale.edu/collections/objects/6746>

– Source 1 Description: Yale University Art Gallery - Information on the Dura Europos Mithraeum display

– Source 2 URL: <http://media.artgallery.yale.edu/duraeuropos/dura.html>

– Source 2 Description: Yale University Art Gallery - Information on the Excavations of Dura Europos

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1934-1935

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Yale-French Excavations at Dura Europos (block J7, Mithraeum), present-day Syria

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

–Other [specify]: No

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: The mithraeum was originally placed in a room within a house (in insula J7), which was later expanded.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: It was located in the NW section of the city, in a building connected to the city wall, near two towers, and among residential blocks. The building was originally a private dwelling.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: It is located near houses.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: NA

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Notes: It is not part of a larger sanctuary.

– Yes

Notes: The mithraeum was originally part of a private residence in an insula (housing block).

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Sacrificial

– Social

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– No

Notes: The mithraeum, in its first phase, was merely repurposing a space.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 168 CE - 210 CE

– Yes

Notes: The subsequent renovations and enlargements of the mithraeum indicate that those maintaining the shrine were creating a space that was more intended to last and adjusting it to the ritual needs of those using it.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 210 CE - 256 CE

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: When the mithraeum was founded in 168 CE, it made use of an existing space within a house. The mithraeum itself only occupied one room entered from an antechamber to the east that connected to a courtyard and a smaller chamber. The mithraeum consisted of a raised central aisle flanked by benches on which columns stood to support the ceiling, which was only 1.65 m high over the benches. On one end of the central aisle (west, opposite the entrance) was the main altar with two smaller altars on the side. The focal point were two tauroctony reliefs (Mithras slaying a bull), which were raised above the floor on a podium approached by a small staircase. It was rebuilt in 210 CE and enlarged, with the removal of the partition wall between the mithraeum and its antechamber and the addition of two more columns. An arched niche was added to the back wall, framing the tauroctonies. A new podium was added and a basin was dug into the middle of the paved aisle. Two small altars were added near this basin as well. Another reconstruction took place in 240 CE, during which the main chamber was made more symmetrical and further enlarged. Further columns were added on top of the benches. A wider podium and seven-stepped staircase was added to the back wall. Mithraea were usually subterranean or semi-subterranean (in imitation of a cave) but the Dura mithraeum stood above ground. Two chambers were added to the north. The roof was probably altered at this time to create a vaulted ceiling (in imitation of a cave) given the addition of several new columns.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Buried

↳ With ritually deposited medium/material:

This might consist of pure sand, or a medium that has been consecrated.

–Yes [specify]: Sand

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–As the result of war

Notes: It was buried in sand in order to strengthen the fortification walls prior to the Sasanid siege of the city in 256.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Other [specify]: No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– More than once

Notes: Reconstructed after a destruction in 210 CE and further reconstructed in 240.

↳ In modernity
– Post-Renaissance

Notes: It was not reconstructed at the site itself but many elements of the mithraeum were relocated and partially reconstructed at the Yale University Art Gallery.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Mithras

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Notes: Although ancillary deities were either worshipped or acknowledged in the cult (Cautes, Cautopates, Luna, etc.) the focus of the cult itself is Mithras.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The Roman Army

Notes: The two tauroctonies dating to 169 and 170/1 CE (first phase) respectively were dedicated by Palmyrene auxiliary troops. The reconstruction in 209 were commissioned by the Legions IV Scythica and XVI Flavia Firma. The building itself was within the castrum (Roman military camp) of Dura Europos.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Other [specify]: Soldiers

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: It was funded by Roman soldiers who were stationed at the Dura castrum.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: As Mithras was worshipped as a protector of the Roman legion, the place was built with the intent that participation in the cult's secret rituals would result in some form of protection from the god.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Brick, worked stone, plaster, etc.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human,

anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: NA

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Notes: Technically, the whole mithraeum is hidden from view, occupying the interior space of a building. As this was a mystery cult, only those participating in the cult would have seen the decorated interior.

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: NA

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

|

↳ Type
– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
– No

↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: NA

↳ Are there mosaics present:
– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

Notes: Some of the inscriptions and dipinti label the figures depicted in the tauroctony reliefs, in this case those who had commissioned the mithraeum. The inscriptions are in Greek and Palmyrene Aramaic.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: NA

- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - Yes
 - Notes: Primarily mythological figures from the Zodiac.

- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - Yes
 - Notes: In addition to being represented anthropomorphically, Sol and Luna are depicted in abstract.

- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No

- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes

- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
 - Notes: A few figures from the tauroctony reliefs and the paintings represent humans, particularly those who commissioned the mithraeum.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: In addition to Mithras slaying the bull, the frescoes also depict Mithras in a hunting scene.

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Real human beings are depicted in association with the god.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: NA

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, since Mithras is conflated with Sol Invictus (the Unconquered Sun).

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: NA

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: Not a statue in this case but the focal point of the cult was the image of the tauroctony at the back wall of the mithraeum.

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Fowl

Notes: A brick-lined cavity in the floor near the podium contained what were probably bird bones--perhaps the remnants of a foundation rite. In addition, there were several small altars found in the mithraeum, indicating that sacrifices could be held. One of the tauroctony reliefs, in addition, also depict a man labelled Zenobios as sacrificing to Mithras.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

Notes: The two votive reliefs dedicated were made of gypsum plaster of local craftsmanship.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: NA

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: NA

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Within the mithraeum (hence the benches)

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions from the site include wine among the expenses of the mithraeum (Rostovtzeff 1939: 124–126).

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: The people who founded the sanctuary seem to have had specialized ritual knowledge acquired from elsewhere, given that they were aware of appropriate rituals/material culture for mithraea.

↳ Present full time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male, as participation was restricted to men.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: Soldiers.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: There seems to have been a ranked hierarchy among initiates, to whom specialized knowledge was imparted as they rose through the ranks.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Inscribed accounts were found at the site of the mithraeum.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No